

COMMON PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS TO TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Abstract. In this article it is highlighted that the problems which new language learners usually encounter and possible solutions to them to make this process fun and enjoyable.

Keywords: english language, technologies, lessons, teachers, second language, solutions, methods, English atmosphere, mistakes.

ОБЩИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ВТОРОМУ

Аннотация. В этой статье подчеркивается, что проблемы, с которыми обычно сталкиваются новые изучающие язык, и возможные решения для них, чтобы сделать этот процесс увлекательным и приятным.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, технологии, уроки, учителя, второй язык, решения, методы, английская атмосфера, ошибки.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, learning foreign languages, especially, English, is seen as number-one priority to succeed in academic and personal life. With the development of new technologies it is not so difficult to find useful sources, information, online lessons, but learners are still struggling with the process and deciding to give up easily.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To understand the teaching and learning procedure we have to look through the challenges they may face and find the best and most powerful ways to overcome. Let's start with common classroom problems:

- Being overly dependent on the teacher.

Most students always see their teachers as the only person who can help them to correct their mistakes or instruct new theme instead of trying themselves and with doing this they will automatically lose their precious time and the chance to put a step to be independent. If they learn how to tackle the small problem on their own, the positive encouragement will be seen on their behavior at the classroom and they will also be able to achieve more.

1. Not keeping the English atmosphere and using first-language.

While teaching English as a second language encouraging learners to use English and only English is really important to fully learn the language itself. In order to solve this problem, teachers can establish a penalty system and prohibit speaking on their native languages which will eventually aid students to become fluent speakers in a short time.

- Boring and uninteresting styles

DISCUSSION

Mostly, boring and old ways of teaching makes students inattentive during the class. With proper planning, use of new advanced technologies, adding colours they can change their lectures to truly interesting process. According to Universal Design for Learning (UDL) adapted from Wehmeyer (2006) for students with mild IDD or mental radiations, the use of digital talking books, text-to speech, graphic depictions, and flow charts allow them with special needs to get included during the lesson.

- Only stressing grammar and not having time to work on other skills.

It is usually common to see learners devoting too much time to learn grammatical structures, and working on other skills like speaking, reading, listening or writing. As a result, they can not speak confidently or express what they really mean to others. In this case, preparing special schedule which consists equal hours of studying on both sections which will make them a confident user of that language.

CONCLUSION

Above listed problems and given solutions will definitely help to teachers and language learners to make hard and difficult processes easy and understandable with using effective tips to achieve their language goals in the near future.

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